

Physico-Chemical Studies of Zinc (II)-Camphorate Complex

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Stoichiometry (1 : 1) of Zn(II)-camphorate complex has been studied by Job's method of continuous variation using conductivity and spectrophotometry as index properties. Stability constant of the complex at pH 4.30 and ionic strength 0.2 is found to be 1.152×10^3 at 27.5° by Bjerrum's method¹ and 1.00×10^3 by Job's method using nonequimolar solutions.

Metal salts of camphoric acid with Cu(II)², Ni(II)², Mn(II)³, W⁴, Ti⁵, Nd⁶, Pr⁶, have been prepared by various workers. Cd(II)-camphorate complex⁷ has already been studied by Job's method of continuous variation and by Bjerrum's method. The present investigation deals with a complete study of composition and stability of Zn(II)-camphorate.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of Zinc-perchlorate: Zinc-perchlorate was prepared by dissolving Zinc-oxide analar in a calculated quantity of perchloric acid (60%) and diluted to a definite volume. Zinc content of the solution was determined⁸. The amount of free perchloric acid present was also determined and this was neutralised by adding the required quantity of standard KOH (carbonate-free).

All the mixtures were kept in a thermostat bath maintaining at $27.5 \pm 1^\circ$ for eight hours to attain equilibrium.

Optical density measurements were made on Beckman DU quartz spectrophotometer with a hydrogen tube source. A Holland Phillips pH meter, model, PR9400 with glass and saturated Calomel Electrode assembly, was employed for pH measurements. Conductometric measurements were made on Doron Conductivity bridge with WTW 1000 cycles oscillator and a dip type conductivity cell.

Job's method⁹ of continuous variation for conductivity and for spectrophotometry was used for the determination of the stoichiometry of the complexes as 1 : 1 (M : L).

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Stability constants

(A) *Job's Method*: Non-equimolar solutions of the metal salt and ligand were mixed and conductivity and optical density measurements were made after equilibrium. The

maxima was obtained at 40%. The stability constant of the complex was calculated⁹ from the equation

$$Ks = \frac{(p-1)(1-2x)}{C[(p+1)x-1]^2}$$

where p is given by the ratio of concentration of ligand to the concentration of metal. We have taken $p = 2$, $x = .40$ and $C = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$.

(B) *pH Titration method using Calvin Bjerrum's technique*¹⁰: Following sets were prepared:

(i) 10 ml. of 0.02 M camphoric acid + 2 ml. of 0.1 M $HClO_4$ + 4.2 ml. of 1 M sodium-perchlorate + 8.8 ml. water.

(ii) 10 ml. of 0.02 M camphoric acid + 2 ml. of 0.1 M $HClO_4$ + 5 ml. of 0.002 M zinc perchlorate + 4.14 ml. of 1 M sodium perchlorate + 3.86 ml. of water.

pH titrations were carried out in an oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere. \bar{n} values were evaluated¹¹ from the horizontal distance on Fig. 1 between the reference curve I and the

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curve II determined in presence of the metal ion. \bar{n} values thus obtained were plotted against pA ($-\log A$) for getting the formation curve¹¹ and the value of stability constant was found to be 1.152×10^3 .

TABLE

Stability constant of Zn(II) Camphorate

Dilution in ml.	pH	ml. of 0.1M alkali	ml. of 0.02M ligand	\bar{n}	Concentration of Ligand Moles/Litre		Concentration of free ligand ion (A)	$\frac{1}{A}$	pA
					Metal bound	Free ligand			
28.15	4.30	.10	.25	.50	1.776×10^{-4}	69.26×10^{-4}	8.686×10^{-4}	1.152×10^3	3.0612
28.30	4.40	.11	.275	.55	1.943×10^{-4}	68.73×10^{-4}	1.366×10^{-3}	7.321×10^2	2.8646
28.45	4.50	.12	.30	.60	2.109×10^{-4}	68.19×10^{-4}	2.148×10^{-3}	4.656×10^2	2.6680
28.60	4.60	.13	.325	.65	2.273×10^{-4}	67.64×10^{-4}	3.377×10^{-3}	2.961×10^2	2.4715
28.75	4.70	.14	.35	.70	2.434×10^{-4}	67.11×10^{-4}	5.310×10^{-3}	1.883×10^2	2.2749
28.90	4.80	.15	.375	.75	2.595×10^{-4}	66.61×10^{-4}	8.352×10^{-3}	1.198×10^2	2.0782
29.40	5.10	.18	.45	.90	3.061×10^{-4}	64.91×10^{-4}	3.243×10^{-2}	3.083×10^1	1.4890
29.50	5.20	.20	.50	1.00	3.391×10^{-4}	64.40×10^{-4}	5.095×10^{-2}	1.963×10^1	1.2928

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